

Utilisation of Information and Communication Technology for effective Instructional Delivery of Mechanical Technology Courses in Universities in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined the utilization of information and communication technology for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. Three specific objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the conduct of the study. The design adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in Rivers State. The population of this study consisted of 44 respondents comprising 12 mechanical technology education lecturers and 32 postgraduate students in mechanical technology in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University, Rumuolumeni. Since the population of the study is of a manageable size, census was adopted. A self-structured questionnaire titled: "Utilisation of Information and Communication Technology for effective instructional delivery of Mechanical Technology Courses in Universities" was used to obtain data from the respondents. The instrument was face and content validated by experts in mechanical technology education in Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient values of 0.88, 0.79 and 0.77 for each of three clusters in the questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation was used to provide answers to the research questions. Decision on each questionnaire item was based on the criterion mean of 2.50. Item with mean value greater than 2.50 was termed as "High Extent" while mean value less than 2.50 was considered as "Low Extent". The null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. Null hypothesis was considered "Significant or Rejected" when the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance otherwise "Not significant or accepted". The study found that that information and communication technologies such as digital devices and software applications are utilized at low extent for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. The study also found that network connectivity as a form of information and communication technologies are highly utilized in the delivery of instruction of mechanical courses in Rivers State Universities. The study recommended that government should make digital devices for teaching and learning of mechanical courses available in universities. This will enhance the utilization of these devices in during instructional delivery.

Keywords: Utilisation, Information and Communication Technology, Instructional delivery, Mechanical Technology

INTRODUCTION

One of the fundamental components of the United Nations' sustainable development 2030 agenda is quality education. It aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all. The implementation of information and communication technology in education have emerged as an essential tool to achieve this goal (Abid, Mohd, Mohd, & Rajiv, 2022). Over the years, the utilization of information and communication technology have shown a powerful impact on the education system. For instance, the recent COVID-19 Pandemic has further institutionalized the applications of digital technologies in education. These digital technologies have made a paradigm shift in the entire education system. Technological improvements in education have made life easier for both lecturers and students to have unhindered access to resources that provides valuable contribution to professional development.

Information and communication technology (ICT) is an umbrella term and consists of all technical means used to handle information and aid communication, including computer and network hardware, communication middleware as well as necessary software. In other words, it encompasses radio, television, fixed and cellular phones, computers and networks, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and applications associated with them (World Business Council for Sustainable Development, 2012). ICT is commonly referred to all technologies used to facilitate communication and information

exchange, including computers, networks, and software. More a decade ago, the emergence of information and communication technologies have led to a paradigm shifts in the way information are being handled, stored retrieved and accessed all over the world. Hence, information and communication technology is a game changer, transforming the means by which interactions occurs especially in teaching and learning.

One of the more outstanding applications of information and communication technologies is in the teaching and learning. The implementation of information and communication technologies has in education delivery has outshined the traditional means of education recently. Through the utilization of information and communication technologies teaching and learning is taken beyond the four walls of an institution extending the possibilities of literacy to those which many be impossible to reach using traditionally medium. For the purpose of this study, extent of the utilization of ICT in the teaching of mechanical courses are being critically examined. The various forms of information and communication technologies considered involved digital devices, network connectivity and software application.

The utilization of digital devices in the instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities has witnessed significant transformations, particularly influenced by ongoing digitalization trends in education. A crucial aspect of this transformation is the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to enhance teaching effectiveness and student engagement. Despite the growing recognition of digital tools, studies indicate that their actual application in pedagogical practices remains variable across institutions. Salifu and Owusu-Acheampong Salifu and Owusu-Acheampong (2021) highlight that while many educators utilize digital technology tools, only a limited number effectively apply these tools for impactful instructional delivery. This finding aligns with López-Belmonte et al., (2023), which assert that contemporary educational environments, when fully optimized with state-of-the-art digital technologies, can significantly enhance student learning experiences. Furthermore, it is essential to understand the role of digital pedagogy in promoting learner-centered institutions, as outlined by Chmyr et al., (2024). Their research indicates that an effective digital infrastructure such as computer, virtual reality, augmented reality, 3D printing alongside continuous improved technologies can significantly elevate motivation among mechanical technology students, making it imperative for universities to foster a positive technology-enhanced learning environment for them.

Complementing this perspective, García-Martín and Sánchez García-Martín & Sánchez (2022) emphasize the necessity for higher education institutions to address gaps in ICT use and digital skills among lecturers, highlighting the importance of investment in both equipment and training (Khan & Abid, 2021). The rapid transition necessitated a rethink of traditional educational methodologies, and professors faced considerable challenges in adapting to this digital landscape due to prior lack of experience with digital tools (Choi & Chung, 2021).

Additionally, the literature reflects on the implications of the digital divide, particularly in the context of socio-economic disparities that influence access to technology and its effective use in education. Antón-Sancho et al. (2023) found that despite an increase in mobile device usage among instructors during the pandemic, various factors contribute to the under-utilization of digital resources. This observation reveals the urgent need for universities to institutionalize mechanisms that ensure equitable access to digital resources, thereby fostering inclusive educational practices.

With emergence of advanced technologies in recent time, effective delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities heavily relies on the utilization of network connectivity. The rise of innovative instructional methodologies underpinned by networked technologies; educators have employed various strategies to enhance student learning outcomes in mechanical engineering classes. One such strategy is the incorporation of virtual simulation technologies. These technologies facilitate a risk-free experimental

environment where students can engage with complex mechanical principles and problem-solving scenarios, leading to improved practical skills and a deeper understanding compared to traditional teaching methods (Wei, et al., 2023). The adaptation of these technologies is becoming increasingly important in the context of mechanical technology education, where the collaboration between simulation software and instructional methods enhances learning experiences. Furthermore, innovative pedagogical approaches centered around network connectivity, such as the implementation of cloud computing and big data course systems, highlight the need for a comprehensive educational framework that utilizes modern ICT tools. These systems can foster an integrated and practical learning experience, as they encourage students to explore and apply theoretical knowledge collaboratively (Zhu, 2023). Such integration aligns with current educational demands and equips students with essential skills for their future careers in engineering (Mnguni & Mokiwa, 2020).

The reliance on online platforms underscores the importance of connectivity in delivering mechanical technology courses, demonstrating the need for institutions to reinforce their digital infrastructure and pedagogical frameworks in response to evolving educational landscapes. In addition, the establishment of collaborative educational environments facilitated by social networks is crucial. Research shows that such platforms enhance peer interactions and foster competitive learning atmospheres, allowing students to take control of their learning process. This not only motivates them but also promotes a sense of community among learners (Yahya & Ahmad, 2018). The effective use of these networks is directly correlated with successful instructional delivery, indicating the necessity of leveraging connectivity within mechanical technology curricula.

The effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities also increasingly relies on the integration of various software applications. These applications contribute significantly to enhancing the learning experience, promoting active engagement, and facilitating collaborative learning environments. Research has established that educational software applications enhance student engagement and learning outcomes in diverse fields, including mechanical technology. For instance, visualization and simulation software have proven to be instrumental in teaching complex mechanical systems. The use of tools like 3D graphics, simulation environments, and modeling programs allows students to interactively engage with abstract concepts, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter (Alameer & Alhussain, 2016; Körtesi et al., 2022). By transitioning to technology-based classrooms, educators can leverage software applications to create a more dynamic and collaborative learning atmosphere, which is essential in technical fields such as mechanical technology (Körtési et al., 2022; Romanova, 2020).

Similarly, the adoption of instructional software must be complemented by appropriate teacher training and professional development. The pedagogical integration of technology is not solely about the availability of software, but also about educators possessing the necessary skills to implement these tools effectively. Studies show that a lack of technological competence among instructors can pose significant barriers to technology integration in education (Doğan et al., 2020; Doğan, 2021). Thus, it is critical to offer comprehensive training programs that equip teachers with both technological and pedagogical knowledge to maximize the potential of software applications in their teaching practices (Doğan et al., 2020).

Student perceptions towards software applications also highlight the importance of technological integration in the classroom. Students express a preference for courses that employ technology as part of instructional delivery, as it aligns with their learning preferences and expectations in a digital age (Green et al., 2015; Ritzhaupt et al., 2012). The incorporation of interactive elements, such as clickers and

collaborative platforms, enhances engagement and facilitates immediate feedback, thereby creating a more responsive learning environment (Hwang & Wolfe, 2010). This preference underscores the necessity for universities to adapt and enhance their mechanical technology curricula by integrating relevant software solutions that resonate with contemporary pedagogical trends and student needs (Xie et al., 2013; Tizón et al., 2021).

Statement of the problem

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has become a critical factor in improving instructional delivery and enhancing learning outcomes worldwide. In the context of higher education, particularly in technical fields such as Mechanical Technology, the adoption and effective use of ICT can significantly improve the quality of instruction, making learning more interactive, accessible, and efficient. Despite the potential benefits, universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, face challenges in fully utilizing ICT for the instructional delivery of Mechanical Technology courses.

As observed by the author, many institutions in Rivers State are confronted with inadequate infrastructure, insufficient ICT training for lecturers, limited access to modern technological tools, and a lack of strategic planning for the integration of ICT into the curriculum. As a result, the adoption of ICT in teaching Mechanical Technology courses remains suboptimal, impacting both the quality of education and the preparedness of students for the demands of the modern workforce.

This problem is further compounded by resistance to change from some lecturers, who may be unfamiliar with ICT tools or reluctant to adapt to new teaching methods. Additionally, students' limited access to ICT resources outside the classroom, due to factors such as inadequate internet connectivity and the high cost of technological devices, restricts their ability to fully benefit from ICT-enhanced learning environments. The absence of a systematic and effective integration of ICT in the delivery of Mechanical Technology courses in universities in Rivers State may hinder the development of essential skills and knowledge required by graduates in this field. Hence, study seeks to explore the extent to which ICT is being utilized in the instructional delivery of Mechanical Technology courses at the university level in Rivers State.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to determine the extent information and communication technologies are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities. In specific terms, the study sought to

1. Examine the extent to which digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities.
2. Determine the extent to which network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities.
3. Investigate the extent to which software applications are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the study

1. To what extent are digital devices utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities?

2. To what extent are network connectivity utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities?
3. To what extent are software applications utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significance between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities
2. There is no significance between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities
3. There is no significance between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent software applications are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted a descriptive survey research design. This research design was adopted because the researcher sought to describe opinion of the respondents to provide answers to the research questions. The study was conducted in Rivers State. This area of the study was considered suitable for the study because there exist various universities offering mechanical courses and accessibility to information and communication technologies. The population of this study consisted of 44 respondents comprising 12 mechanical technology education lecturers and 32 postgraduate students in mechanical technology in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University, Rumuolumeni. Since the population of the study is of a manageable size, census was adopted. That is, the entirety of the population was involved in the study. A self-structured questionnaire titled: “Utilisation of Information and Communication Technology for effective instructional delivery of Mechanical Technology Courses in Universities (UICTEIDMTCU)” was used obtain data from the respondents. The questionnaire was designed in a four 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed, Strongly Disagreed with a response scale value of 4,3,2, and 1. The questionnaire contained 19 items which elicited information on each of the research questions. The instrument was face and content validated by experts in mechanical technology education in Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient values of 0.88, 0.79 and 0.77 for each of three clusters in the questionnaire. Out of the 44 copies of questionnaire distributed, only 35 copies of the questionnaire (8 lecturers and 27 post-graduate students) were retrieved and used for analysis. Mean and standard deviation was used to provide answers to the research questions. Decision on each questionnaire item was based on the criterion mean of 2.50. Item with mean value greater than 2.50 was termed as “High Extent” while mean value less than 2.50 was considered as “Low Extent”. The null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. Null hypothesis was considered “Significant or Rejected” when the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance otherwise “Not significant or accepted”

RESULT

Research Questions 1: To what extent are digital devices utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers state?

Table 1: Mean Responses on the Extent Digital Devices Utilized for Effective Instructional Delivery of Mechanical Technology Courses in Universities

S/N	Items	Lecturers=8			Students=27		
		Mean	S.D	Rm	Mean	S.D	Rm
1	The utilization of interactive whiteboards allows instructors to present content interactively, write notes, and demonstrate mechanical concepts in real-time.	2.47	1.01	LE	2.24	1.04	LE
2	Computer devices are used by lecturers to equip students with the skills in engine design and modeling	2.78	0.78	HE	2.34	1.03	LE
3	VR and AR technologies are often used to immerse students in virtual environments where they can simulate mechanical systems, machinery, and even industrial settings	2.11	0.67	LE	2.01	0.89	LE
4	3D Printers is used to create physical models and prototypes of mechanical designs that students work on.	2.07	0.58	LE	2.08	0.67	LE
5	Document cameras and projectors are used by instructors to project notes, diagrams, and drawings onto a screen, allowing them to explain concepts clearly.	2.89	0.87	HE	2.71	0.45	HE
6	Digital devices such as digital calipers, thermocouples, oscilloscopes, and other tools are used for accurate measurement and data collection in mechanical labs	2.23	0.74	LE	2.21	1.08	LE
7	Digital versions of textbooks and supplementary learning materials, are utilized for students' access course materials from anywhere	2.32	0.67	LE	2.27	0.69	LE
8	Podcasting and multimedia resources are often used to explain mechanical principles and understand complex topics and which allows for learning flexibility	2.45	0.58	LE	2.31	1.03	LE
Grand Mean & S.D.		2.42	0.74		2.27	0.86	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 revealed the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent digital devices utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. The grand mean (2.42 & 2.27) of the responses of both respondents showed that to a low extent digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers state. By comparing the criterion mean of 2.50 to the item means in table 1, it was found that majority of digital devices identified in the table were been utilized to a low extent for instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers state. The standard deviation scores of 0.74 and 0.86 shows how closely or widely spread the scores are to the average.

Research Question 2: To what extent are network connectivity utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities?

Table 2: Mean responses on the Extent Network Connectivity Utilized for Effective Instructional Delivery of Mechanical Technology Courses in Universities

S/N	Items	Lecturers=8			Students=27		
		Mean	S.D.	Rm	Mean	S.D.	Rm
1	High-speed internet is essential for accessing resources, online simulations, and video lectures for the achievement of instructional objectives	3.10	0.71	HE	2.92	1.00	HE
2	Video conferencing tools supports real-time interaction and student collaboration on mechanical projects, especially in hybrid or fully online learning environments	2.92	0.82	HE	2.55	1.01	HE
3	Collaborative online platforms allow students to collaborate on mechanical technology projects, discuss concepts, and share design files	2.54	0.73	HE	2.61	1.06	HE
4	Online platforms such as Turnitin, or enable online assessments, quizzes, and exams for mechanical technology courses.	2.59	0.73	HE	2.91	0.87	HE
5	Social media networks like LinkedIn, ResearchGate, or Twitter are used by instructors and students to connect with industry professionals, share knowledge, and discuss current trends in mechanical technology.	2.67	0.98	HE	2.70	0.98	HE
6	Institutional repository and research databases are used to smooth access to academic resources ensures that students can stay updated on the latest research and trends in mechanical technology	2.76	1.03	HE	2.59	1.03	HE
Grand Mean & S.D.		2.76	0.83		2.71	0.99	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 presented the mean responses on the extent network connectivity utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. The criterion means of 2.50 showed that majority of the items listed in table 2 were rated as high extent since they have mean responses higher than the criterion mean. The grand mean of 2.76 and 2.71 shows that to a high extent network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. The standard deviation scores of 0.83 and 0.899 shows how closely or widely spread the scores are to the average.

Research Question 3: To what extent are software applications utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Responses on the extent Software Applications utilized for effective Instructional Delivery of Mechanical Technology Courses in Universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Lecturers=8			Students=27		
		Mean	S.D.	Rm	Mean	S.D	Rm
1	Computer-Aided Design (CAD) Software such as AutoCAD are used for creating 2D and 3D designs of mechanical parts and systems to help develop essential deign skills.	2.49	0.53	LE	2.51	1.06	HE
2	Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAM) Software allows students to design and simulate manufacturing processes in the classroom	2.19	0.81	LE	2.32	0.76	LE
3	MATLAB is often used for numerical computations, simulations, and modeling of mechanical systems	2.17	0.19	LE	2.19	0.59	LE
4	A 3D printing software that helps students prepare models for 3D printing, which is a vital skill in modern mechanical technology.	2.26	0.15	LE	2.34	1.09	LE
5	Project management tool that helps students organize their mechanical design projects, assign tasks, and track deadlines	2.15	0.09	LE	2.46	1.01	LE
6	Measurement and analysis software for acquiring and analyzing data from various mechanical systems in laboratory settings.	2.23	0.71	LE	2.09	0.85	LE
Grand Mean & S.D.		2.25	0.41		2.32	0.89	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 presents the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which software applications are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. The grand mean of 2.25 and 2.32 shows that majority of the items in table 3 were rated “low extent” since the grand mean is lower than the benchmark mean of 2.50. However, students’ responses in one of the items revealed at high extent Computer-Aided Design (CAD) Software such as AutoCAD are used for creating 2D and 3D designs of mechanical parts and systems to help develop essential deign skills.

Test of Hypotheses

1. There is no significance between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State

Table 4: z-test on the extent digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of Mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State

Categories	N	Mean	S.D.	Df	α	z-cal	z-crit	p-value	Remark
Lecturers	8	2.42	0.74	33	0.05	0.29	2.00	0.54	Accept
Students	27	2.27	0.88						

Source: Research Data, 2025

Table 4 shows the z-test analysis on the extent digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. At 0.05 level of significance and degrees of freedom 33, the z-critical value of the analysis is 2.00. The z-calculated value obtained was 0.29 which is less than the critical value. Also, the p-value of 0.54 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Since the p-value is greater than the level of significance, the null hypothesis therefore was accepted. This revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State

2. There is no significance between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State

Table 5: z-test on the extent Network Connectivity are Utilized for Effective Instructional Delivery of Mechanical Technology Courses in Universities in Rivers State

Categories	N	Mean	S.D.	Df	α	z-cal	z-crit	p-value	Remark
Lecturers	8	2.76	0.83	33	0.05	0.76	2.00	0.21	Accept
Students	27	2.71	0.99						

Source: Research Data, 2025

Table 5 shows the z-test analysis on the extent network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. At 0.05 level of significance and degrees of freedom 33, the z-critical value of the analysis is 2.00. The z-calculated value obtained was 0.76 which is less than the critical value of 2.00. Also, the analysis showed that p-value of 0.21 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Since the p-value is greater than the level of significance, the null hypothesis therefore was accepted. This revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State

3. There is no significance between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent software applications are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State

Table 4: z-test on the extent Software Application are Utilized for Effective Instructional Delivery of Mechanical technology Courses in Universities in Rivers State

Categories	N	Mean	S.D.	Df	α	z-cal	z-crit	p-value	Remark
Lecturers	8	2.25	0.41	33	0.05	0.57	2.00	0.19	Accept
Students	27	2.32	0.89						

Source: Research Data, 2025

Table 4 shows the z-test analysis on the extent software application are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. At 0.05 level of significance and degrees of freedom 33, the z-critical value of the analysis is 2.00. The z-calculated value obtained was 0.57 which is less than the critical value, and the p-value of 0.19 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Since the p-value is greater than the level of significance, the null hypothesis therefore was accepted. This shows that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent software application are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State.

Discussion of findings

Findings from table 1 showed that to a low extent digital devices are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers state. The responses of both categories of respondents in Rivers State universities indicated that to a low extent utilization of interactive whiteboards allows instructors to present content interactively, write notes, and demonstrate mechanical concepts in real-time. The respondent further had it that to low extent computer devices are used by lecturers to equip students with the skills in engine design and modeling Universities. Lecturers and students both recorded that virtual reality and augmented reality technologies, 3D printers amongst others are not used for instructional delivery of mechanical courses in Rivers State. The findings are consistent with Antón-Sancho et al. (2023) in their study found that despite an increase in mobile device usage among instructors during the pandemic, various factors contribute to the under-utilization of digital resources. In addition, Salifu and Owusu-Acheampong Salifu and Owusu-Acheampong (2021) highlight that while many educators utilize digital technology tools, only a limited number effectively apply these tools for impactful instructional delivery.

Findings from table 2 revealed that to a high extent network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers state. The responses of the lecturers and postgraduate students showed that to a high extent network connectivity are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. The findings showed that high-speed internet is often utilized for accessing resources, online simulations, and video lectures for the achievement of instructional objectives. The study also showed that video conferencing tools supports real-time interaction and student collaboration on mechanical projects, especially in hybrid or fully online learning environments. The findings of the study are in agreement with Wei, et al., (2023) network connectivity where students can engage with complex mechanical principles and problem-solving scenarios, leading to improved practical skills and a deeper understanding compared to traditional teaching methods is utilized at a very low extent in some part subsharan Africa.

Lastly, findings from research question 3 as presented in table 3 showed that to a low extent software applications are utilized for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers state. Lecturers and students indicated that to a low extent; Computer-Aided Design (CAD) Software such as AutoCAD are used for creating 2D and 3D designs of mechanical parts and systems to help develop essential design skills, Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAM) Software allows students to design and simulate manufacturing processes in the classroom, MATLAB is often used for numerical computations, simulations, and modeling of mechanical systems amongst others. This finding is in alignment with Alameer and Alhussain, (2016) who posited that the use of tools like 3D graphics, simulation environments, and modeling programs allows students to interactively engage with abstract concepts, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter. In support of the view, Körtesi et al., (2022) maintained that transitioning to technology-based classrooms, educators can leverage software applications to create a more dynamic and collaborative learning atmosphere, which is essential in technical fields such as mechanical technology.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that information and communication technologies such as digital devices and software applications are utilized at low extent for effective instructional delivery of mechanical technology courses in universities in Rivers State. The study also concludes that network connectivity as a form of information and communication technologies are highly utilized in the delivery of instruction of mechanical courses in Rivers State Universities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings of the study, it was recommended that;

1. Government should make digital devices for teaching and learning of mechanical courses available in universities. This will enhance the utilization of these devices in during instructional delivery.
2. School administrators should provide more support for lecturers by funding their network connectivity sometimes. This funding will further encourage them to utilize high internet, video conferencing tool, collaboration tools and social media for instructional delivery in Rivers State Universities
3. Lecturers should as well ensure that software application such as computer aided design software, MATLAB, 3D printing software are used for instructions delivery, therefore it is essential that lecturers are trained on how to make use of computer application in mechanical courses.

References

- Abid H., Mohd J., Mohd A.Q., & Rajiv S. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review, *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, Volume 3, 2022, 275-285,
- Alameer, M. & Alhussain, T. (2016). Students' engagement in educational software: a comparison between narrative and traditional styles. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(4), 322-326. <https://doi.org/10.7763/ijiet.2016.v6.707>

- Antón-Sancho, Á., Fernández-Arias, P., & Vergara, D. (2023). Impact of the covid-19 pandemic on the use of ict tools in science and technology education. *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 13(1), 130. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jotse.1860>
- Chmyr, V., Копєхов, А., ПєбОЛ, С., & Partyka, S. (2024). Fostering digital transformations in military engineering education: introduction of a technology-enhanced learning environment. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 82(2), 162-185. <https://doi.org/10.33225/pec/24.82.162>
- Choi, L. & Chung, S. (2021). Navigating online language teaching in uncertain times: challenges and strategies of efl educators in creating a sustainable technology-mediated language learning environment. *Sustainability*, 13(14), 7664. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147664>
- Doğan, S. (2021). Teachers' skills to integrate technology in education: two path models explaining instructional and application software use.. <https://doi.org/10.3102/1691726>
- Doğan, S., Dogan, N., & Çelik, İ. (2020). Teachers' skills to integrate technology in education: two path models explaining instructional and application software use. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(1), 1311-1332. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10310-4>
- García-Martín, J. & Sánchez, J. (2022). The digital divide of know-how and use of digital technologies in higher education: the case of a college in Latin america in the covid-19 era. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(6), 3358. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19063358>
- Green, A., Chang, W., Tanford, S., & Moll, L. (2015). Student perceptions towards using clickers and lecture software applications in hospitality lecture courses. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 15(1), 29-47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15313220.2014.999738>
- Hwang, J. & Wolfe, K. (2010). Implications of using the electronic response system in a large class. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 10(3), 265-279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15313220.2010.503536>
- Khan, Z. & Abid, M. (2021). Distance learning in engineering education: challenges and opportunities during covid-19 pandemic crisis in Pakistan. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020720920988493>
- Körtesi, P., Simonka, Z., Szabó, Z., Gunčaga, J., & Neag, R. (2022). Challenging examples of the wise use of computer tools for the sustainability of knowledge and developing active and innovative methods in steam and mathematics education. *Sustainability*, 14(20), 12991. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142012991>
- López-Belmonte, J., Pozo-Sánchez, S., Guerrero, A., & Λαμπρόπουλος, Γ. (2023). Metaverse in education: a systematic review. *Revista De Educación a Distancia (Red)*, 23(73). <https://doi.org/10.6018/red.511421>
- Mnguni, L. & Mokiwa, H. (2020). The integration of online teaching and learning in stem education as a response to the covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 19(6A), 1040-1042. <https://doi.org/10.33225/jbse/20.19.1040>

- Ritzhaupt, A., Dawson, K., & Cavanaugh, C. (2012). An investigation of factors influencing student use of technology in k-12 classrooms using path analysis. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 46(3), 229-254. <https://doi.org/10.2190/ec.46.3.b>
- Romanova, I. (2020). Methodological aspects of the use of software in the teaching of engineering disciplines: tasks, problems and prospects. *Itm Web of Conferences*, 35, 04020. <https://doi.org/10.1051/itmconf/20203504020>
- Salifu, I. & Owusu-Acheampong, E. (2021). Improving higher education instructional delivery in the developing world: the role of university teachers as digital leaders. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.100546>
- Tizón, J., Sierra, P., León, L., Navarro, E., Vilá, J., & Moral, J. (2021). Developing a new tool to implement computer-supported active learning strategies in the engineering classroom. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2104.10118>
- Wei, N., Song, T., & Luo, F. (2023). Application of virtual simulation technology in teaching complex engineering mechanics problems. *Frontiers in Educational Research*, 6(29). <https://doi.org/10.25236/fer.2023.062903>
- World Business Council for Sustainable Development (2012). Information communication technology: An enabler for inclusive business solution. Retrieved from https://docs.wbcsd.org/2012/08/Information_Communication_Technology.pdf
- Xie, T., Tillmann, N., & Halleux, J. (2013). Educational software engineering: where software engineering, education, and gaming meet., 36-39. <https://doi.org/10.1109/gas.2013.6632588>
- Yahya, S. & Ahmad, S. (2018). Preliminary study on educational user interface architecture for social network. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(4.36), 457-462. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i4.36.23916>
- Zhu, G. (2023). Construction of cloud computing and big data course teaching system based on cdio. *Curriculum and Teaching Methodology*, 6(18). <https://doi.org/10.23977/curtm.2023.061819>